

On 1,3,5-Triazines. Part—II : Synthesis of 2,4-Dithio-3,5-Diaryl-6-Phenylimino-Hexahydro-1,3,5-Triazines and 2,6-Dithio-3,5-Diaryl-4-Phenylimino-Hexahydro-1,3,5-Triazines

P. P. PATHE†, (Miss) MANIK W. AMBEKAR, N. M. NIMDEOKAR and M. G. PARANJPE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

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New synthetic procedures are reported for the preparation of 2,4-dithio-3,5-diaryl-6-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines (III) and 2,6-dithio-3,5-diaryl-4-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazines (IV), respectively. The formation of 1,3,5-triazines, viz. IIIa and IVa, incidentally has settled the structural problem of the reaction product of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and phenyl thiocarbamide.

I NTERACTION of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I)¹ and phenyl thiocarbamide (II) afforded a product², m.p. 218°. On reaction with benzyl chloride followed by basification, 2-mercaptobenzyl derivative, m.p. 136°, has been isolated. Earlier, a structure 2,4-dithio-3,5-diphenyl-6-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IIIa) was assigned to this product. Afterwards, a new structure 2,6-dithio-3,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IVa)³ has been suggested to this reaction product, on the basis of the formation of identical 2-mercapto benzyl (free base) derivative², m.p. 136°, by the interaction of I and S-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide.

We have now successfully synthesized IIIa and IVa independently, former by the interaction of benzyl phenylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate (VIa) and phenyl isothiocyanate (VII) and the latter by the interaction of 1,5-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (VIIIa) and phenyl isocyanodichloride (IX)⁶. These two syntheses have finally settled the structural problem of the reaction product of phenyl thiocarbamide and N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride². The present communication is the record of these studies.

(I) *Synthesis of 2,4-dithio-3,5-diphenyl-6-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IIIa)*: Benzyl phenylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate⁴ on reaction with

phenyl isothiocyanate at 140-150° afforded a yellow semi-solid, which on several triturations with petroleum ether followed by ethanol was converted into a solid, crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 255°. The product has been assigned structure IIIa on the basis of the following facts.

It was non-desulphurizable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On pyrolysis, smell of phenyl isothiocyanate was quite perceptible. On mixing with the product, m.p. 218°² it depressed its m.p. The ir spectrum of the product clearly indicated the presence of $\nu_{C=N}$ (1675 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{C=S}$ (1070 cm^{-1}) and ν_{-NH} (3225 cm^{-1}) stretching frequencies.

The same reaction of benzyl phenylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate, when extended to *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate, yielded the related 1,3,5-triazine (IIIb), m.p. 216°.

The reaction may be stated as follows :

where R = (a) phenyl and (b) *p*-tolyl

(II) *Synthesis of 2,6-dithio-3,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IVa)*: 1,5-Diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret⁵ on reaction with phenyl isocyanodichloride (IX)⁶ in boiling benzene offered a dark yellow unstable solid, m.p. 65° (d), which on trituration with petroleum ether followed by ethanol isomerized into a white solid crystallized from chlorobenzene, m.p. 220°. It has been assigned the structure IVa on the basis of the following chemical transformations and ir spectral data.

The product was soluble in alkali and could be reprecipitated unchanged on acidification. This indicated the presence of a thiol (-SH). It was

† Present address: National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nagpur-440 020.

414.6. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4S_2$, HCl requires N, 13.22; S, 15.11%; Eq. wt. 424.5). On reaction with aqueous picric acid this afforded a picrate crystallizable from ethanol, m.p. 240° (Found: N, 16.15; S, 10.24. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4S_2$, $C_6H_5N_3O_7$ requires N, 15.91; S, 10.39%).

This on treatment with ethanol isomerised into a solid (2.9 g), crystallized from chlorobenzene, m.p. 220° (Found: N, 14.24; S, 16.16. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires N, 14.43; S, 16.49%). This was identified as 2,6-dithio-3,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IVa).

When the reaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride was extended to other 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (VIIIb-VIIIe), the corresponding 1,3,5-dithiazines (Xb-Xe) were isolated. Because of their unstable nature, these could not be purified. All these have been successfully isomerised into the corresponding 1,3,5-triazines (IVb-IVe) on prolonged treatment with ethanol (Table I).

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